

**Thermal Decomposition and Kinetics of
Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with
2-Hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone
Thiosemicarbazone**

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*Manuscript received 25 October 1990, revised 6 May 1991,
accepted 27 May 1991*

THE thermal decomposition and dehydration reactions of aqua-acido-complexes with organic ligands are of great theoretical interest. However, kinetic studies on different steps of such reactions of coordination compounds are rather rare. For this reason and because of our interest in the thermal behaviour of metal complexes with sulphur ligands^{1,2}, the present investigation was undertaken.

Experimental

Analytical grade reagents were used. The ligand, 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone thiosemicarbazone (L2H) was synthesised by refluxing a 1 : 1 mixture of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone and thiosemicarbazide in methanol for 2 h and recrystallising the product from methanol. For the preparation of the complexes, a hot aqueous solution of the respective metal acetate (10 mmol) was added dropwise to a refluxing methanolic solution of the ligand (10 mmol) containing sodium acetate (1.0 g), and the mixture refluxed for 1 h. The resulting solid complexes were washed with water and methanol and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 . The complexes having general formula $M(L)_1/2H_2O$, where $M = Co^{II}$ or Ni^{II} and $L =$ bivalent anion of the ligand L2H, were characterised² by elemental analyses, conductance, magnetic and spectral data.

The thermoanalytical measurements were performed on a DuPont 990 thermal analyser system in conjunction with 951 thermogravimetric analyser and 1200-901 modular DTA cell system. The operational characteristics are: heating rate, 10 K min^{-1} ; sample size, 2 to 6 mg; atmosphere, static

air; crucible, platinum. The numerical analyses of the thermogravimetric data were performed using a program written in Microsoft BASIC for an IBM computer using DOS 4.00.

Results and Discussion

The instrumental TG traces were redrawn as fraction decomposed (α) against temperature (T) curves to get the primary α - T data. The TG, DTG and DTA traces of $\text{Co(L).1/2H}_2\text{O}$ are shown in Fig. 1. Similar curves were obtained in the case of $\text{Ni(L).1/2H}_2\text{O}$. Both complexes showed three stages

Fig. 1. Thermal curves for $\text{Co(L).1/2 H}_2\text{O}$: (—) TG, (···) DTG and (---) DTA.

in their TG, DTG and DTA, the first of them being the dehydration. The decomposition reactions of both the anhydrous complexes were subjected to non-isothermal kinetic studies and the parameters such as the overall order of reaction (n), apparent activation energy (E), the pre-exponential factor (A) and entropy of activation (ΔS) were evaluated. The weighted least-squares method (weighted LSM) was used for fitting the data to various equations and to evaluate the kinetic parameters; the details are reported in earlier work¹.

The order of the decomposition reaction was determined by computing the correlation coefficient (r) using weighted LSM for the equations suggested by Coats and Redfern³, by differential method using the Freeman-Carroll equation⁴ and by the approximation method suggested by Horowitz and Metzger⁵ for which a 'master curve' was constructed as reported in the literature⁶. The kinetic parameters for both the stages of decomposition of these complexes have been computed by the weighted LSM using the general approach^{1,7} as well as using the equations of Coats-Redfern³, Freeman-Carroll⁴ and Horowitz-Metzger⁵ as described in earlier work¹. All the weighted least-squares plots for the Horowitz-Metzger equation were drawn discarding the first few points (upto $\alpha=0.15$) since they did not fall on the line and hence their inclusion would have

resulted in poor correlation (Fig. 2). In all cases ΔS was calculated using the equation.

$$\Delta S = R \ln [Ah/kT_p]$$

where R is the gas constant, k the Boltzmann constant, h the Planck constant and T_p the DTG peak temperature.

Fig. 2. Weighted least-squares plot for the Horowitz-Metzger equation for the first (a and b) and second (c and d) stages of $\text{Co(L).1/2H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ni(L).1/2H}_2\text{O}$ respectively.

Both the complexes have three-staged weight-loss pattern in TG and are stable upto around 330 K. The elimination of lattice-held water molecules takes place in the first stage, represented by the DTG and endothermic DTA peaks in the range 360–410 K. The initial weight-loss in TG for these complexes agree well with the theoretically expected loss due to the elimination of half a molecule of water from each complex molecule. The anhydrous Co^{II} complex thus formed is found to be stable upto 510 K, while the anhydrous Ni^{II} complex undergoes decomposition only at 530 K. The first stage of decomposition, which takes place between 510 and 635 K in case of the Co^{II} complex and between 530 and 660 K in case of the Ni^{II} complex, is respectively represented by the DTG peaks at 598 and 621 K and exothermic DTA peaks at 595 and 620 K. The final stage of decomposition takes place between 700 and 885 K and are represented by the DTG peaks at 805 and 819 K and the corresponding exothermic DTA peaks at 808 and 822 K for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes respectively. The final stable decomposition products were analysed to be the oxides of the formulae Co_3O_4 and NiO for the respective complexes. The weight-loss data obtained from thermogravimetric studies were compared with that obtained from independent pyrolysis experiments in which the complexes taken in silica crucible were heated in air to about 900 K. The weight-loss data obtained from both TG (72.5 and 74.5%) and independent pyrolysis experiments (72.01 and 73.98%) agree well

TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXES OBTAINED FROM USING GENERAL APPROACH (F_1) AND EQUATIONS OF COATS-REDFERN (CR), FREEMAN-CARROLL (FC) AND HOROWITZ-METZGER (HM)

Compd.	Decomposition stage	Equation	Parameters			
			E kJ mol ⁻¹	A s ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	r
Co(L).1/2H ₂ O	First	F_1	150.6	5.7×10^{13}	-6.5	0.999 8
		CR	146.0	2.8×10^{13}	-12.3	0.999 9
		FC	154.7	6.7×10^{13}	-5.1	0.999 7
		HM	159.2	4.4×10^{13}	-8.7	0.999 8
	Second	F_1^*	182.9	2.0×10^{13}	-17.7	0.999 9
		CR	174.8	7.0×10^{10}	-45.5	0.999 9
		FC	187.4	9.6×10^{11}	-23.8	0.999 8
		HM	192.2	1.1×10^{12}	-23.0	0.999 6
Ni(L).1/2H ₂ O	First	F_1	134.9	7.4×10^{11}	-23.8	1.000 0
		CR	129.8	3.4×10^{10}	-49.5	0.999 9
		FC	140.3	1.1×10^{11}	-40.0	0.999 7
		HM	143.4	5.2×10^{11}	-26.8	0.999 7
	Second	F_1^*	169.5	1.7×10^{11}	-38.5	0.999 9
		CR	161.1	5.3×10^9	-67.2	0.999 8
		FC	171.0	9.8×10^{10}	-42.9	0.999 8
		HM	178.5	7.7×10^{10}	-44.9	0.999 4

with the theoretical values (72.25 and 74.15%) for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes respectively, which confirms the purity of the complexes.

The weighted least-squares plots for the different types of functions available in literature^{1,7} against reciprocal absolute temperature show that the F_1 mechanism gives the best linear fit (with a maximum value of r) in all the cases. The analyses of data obtained from using the Coats-Redfern, Freeman-Carroll and Horowitz-Metzger equations indicates that both stages of decomposition of the complexes follow first order kinetics. Accordingly, the kinetic parameters were evaluated using the weighted LSM for the above mentioned equations and are listed in Table 1 along with the values obtained for the F_1 mechanism by the general approach. The satisfactory values of r (≈ 1) in all the cases indicate good agreement with the experimental data. The values of kinetic parameters obtained by means of the general approach and by the equations of Coats-Redfern, Freeman-Carroll and Horowitz-Metzger show that the general agreement between these methods is good. The ΔS values for both the stages of decomposition of the two complexes are negative which indicates that the activated complex has a more ordered structure than the reactants and that the reactions are slower than normal⁸.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor C. G. R. Nair, Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Kerala, and to Dr. M. P. Kannan, Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, for helpful discussions.

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